

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHAY****FIRST NAME: THEWODROS****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Steps in writing essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Structure of essay (EUCLID 2024, 10-11)
3. Guides for effective writing (EUCLID 2024, 11-14)
4. Citations in avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34-39)
5. Features of style guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-57)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Before starting the ACA-401D course, I reviewed the details of the EUCLID student orientation documents, including the important notes on plagiarism, the sample documents, and the checklists. In the process, I learned how to access the two major websites - Course Management System (CMS) and Learning Management System (LMS)-navigate through the websites and complete all the required sections to start the first course.

I started this course with great enthusiasm as it is my dream of doing my Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). I have a great ambition to occupy myself in reading more resources in my public health field. I reviewed the course roadmap, which helped me access online course packages more. I have read all chapters of the course pack for period one and watched the two videos that are found in the period one folder.

As this was my first experience, I struggled not to miss much of the information from the orientation documents and the information shared by my instructor. I triangulated all available information as it is basic to move smoothly on to the coming sessions and courses.

In this response paper, I summarized the five major concepts, which include steps in writing essays, the structure of the essay, guides for effective writing, citations in avoiding plagiarism, and features of the style guide.

2) STEPS IN WRITING AN ESSAY

The core points of this ACA-401D course pack are found in Chapter One. After we learned all the principles and rules of essay writing discussed in the rest of the chapters, the end goal was to write high-quality papers. In a sense, early start-ups of writing essays have paramount advantages to having enough time for reading various articles, researching topics, defining questions, drafting initial planning and analyzing tasks, critical thinking, and writing (EUCLID 2024, 7).

I agree that proper time management is an essential component in writing academic scholarly. On top of that, knowing the critical steps of writing essays would be a good synergy for managing time. I feel that a problem-solving study starts with a question about a certain problem. In that matter, analyzing the key question, defining key terms, and establishing points of view would be the first basic steps that should come before selecting a topic. Using credible academic sources, the next step is selection of the topic and taking notes from the preliminary readings. The main writing step requires the development of a feasible essay plan with organized ideas (EUCLID 2024, 8).

3) STRUCTURE OF ESSAY

In the writing process, understanding the skeleton and contents of an essay is crucial for a researcher. Broadly, the structure and framework of essays are categorized into three parts: introduction, body, and conclusion. The contents of the introduction should move from general to specific, which includes introducing the topic area with broad opening sentences, answering the question with a thesis statement, and providing a summary or 'road map' of the essay.

The body part of the essay is composed of other sub-components, including objectives, methodology, results, and discussion. In the body part, we answer our research questions by developing discussions, expositions, and evidence to develop our arguments and use relevant examples and authoritative quotes. The conclusion moves from specific to general, under which we restate our answer to the question and re-summarize our main points by including a final, broad statement about possible implications and future directions for research (EUCLID 2024, 10).

In the construction of our arguments, essay paragraphs should deal with one main point or aspect of our answer. It should contain topic sentences of main or controlling ideas, supporting sentences and evidence, analysis and interpretation of evidence, comments on the implication or significance, and a critical conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 11).

4) GUIDES FOR EFFECTIVE WRITING

Some of the principles, tips, and rules for writing essays are presented in separate places in the chapter. I believe that these contents include tips for effective writing, key points in editing essays, handling essays, and rules of thumb that should be consolidated as one section as a guideline.

From the tips in the effective writing section, I concurred with the idea that the early start of writing cuts down on anxiety, beats procrastination, and gives time to develop ideas. Also, writing an essay from beginning to end in a single study session would result in a poor-quality paper. I agreed with starting the body and working paragraph by paragraph; I also agreed with putting the essay aside for a few days as it allows us to consider the essay with a fresh eye. I complied with the idea of writing the introduction and conclusion after the body, knowing what the essay was about. Keeping the essay's question in mind helps us not to lose track of working out the argument (EUCLID 2024, 11).

Nevertheless, essays dramatically improved upon careful editing. In the editing process, it is extremely important to answer the research question directly and comprehensively, ensure arguments make sense, evidence is relevant to and supportive of the arguments, a consistent citation style is used, ensure all quotes and paraphrases are referenced correctly, and all instructions followed properly, remaining within the set word limit. I concluded that checking the overall structure of the essay, logical sequence of paragraphs, sequence of ideas, punctuation, spelling, and transitional signals has the benefit of having a good quality paper (EUCLID 2024, 12).

Additionally, I consented to the rules of thumb in writing effective essays as essential principles of essay writing. I agree that papers should critically assess some important aspects of theories. Also, we should not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping generalities.

Operationally, if a sentence occupies more than five lines, we must find a way to divide it up; if a paragraph goes on for more than 20 lines, we need to find a way to divide it up; if my paper falls into sections, we must include a sentence or two of connective tissue between the sections. Therefore, writing should focus readers' attention on the ideas we wish to express, not on the words we have chosen to express those ideas.

Meanwhile, we should not make the writing boring and clumsy. Like, we should not start every sentence with the subject, use passive constructions, have too many sentences that begin "It is..." or "There is....," repeat the same words, and avoid long strings of prepositional clauses. As a rule, we should only quote a passage if the passage plays an important role in the paper. Like, it is a passage that we will want to be able to refer to at various points in the argument. We should take the views we are discussing seriously (EUCLID 2024, 13-14).

5) CITATION IN AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

I assumed that plagiarism can only happen by deliberate copying and using complete or part of the contents of others' papers. However, it is a bit complex when we think of unintentional plagiarism.

As far as a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information, it is plagiarism. Expressly, it includes taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. When someone writes a paper for us and then puts our name on it and gives it to our professor, it would be plagiarism. Therefore, plagiarism is a wrong, unethical action and a serious academic offense that should be avoided (EUCLID 2024, 34).

To evade plagiarism, we can apply different techniques, such as citation, which is the key one. In simple terms, citation is a method used to indicate where a piece of information came from. The in-text citations and list of works cited are the two types of citations that are discussed in depth in the text.

When we are citing the piece of work within the actual text itself by putting the authors and page number in parenthesis, it is called in-text citations. The more common things that we would like to cite using this method are the exact words of an author and paraphrasing ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in our own words.

When we use a quotation, we must use quotation marks "....." to capture what the author has said. We should not use quotation marks for long quotations with over four lines. They should be indented and look like separate little paragraphs. On the contrary, we should limit the use of quotations; rather, we should use them when there is strong language in the quote and an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader. On the other hand, our paraphrases must look very different to how the author originally wrote it. We should apply our own writing style and words with an accurate representation of the author's ideas (EUCLID 2024, 35-37).

A list of works cited is the other type of citation, which is the 'bibliography' or the 'references' listed at the end of the book. It provides publication information for each of the sources that were cited in the paper. We should use different formats for citing books and online works. Unlike footnote referencing, footnote referencing is the other citation type that has its own standard formats. When we use the footnote method, we do not need to add "References" at the end of our paper (EUCLID 2024, 38-39).

6) FEATURES OF A STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting our approach as writers to certain elements of writing styles that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with

certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting.

Style can encompass many different aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, trademark or branding considerations.

EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized rules are fine. EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted (EUCLID 2024, 41).

7) CONCLUSION

After covering this session, I perceive that writing a high-quality paper requires many steps, protocols, and expertise, as discussed in the course pack. My confidence increased when I think of writing other upcoming papers using the knowledge gained from this course. Despite the five major concepts discussed in the previous paragraphs, all the contents and chapters of the course pack are critically important. I will refer to them again and again when I write response papers, major papers, and main research projects.

Nonetheless, I was a bit confused about the first step in writing an essay from the course pack. Still, I assumed that it should start by defining a question (not by selecting a topic) as it is presented in the pyramid. The narratives in that section should be consistent with the contents of the pyramid. On the contrary, the discussions related to citations are not clear as the focus is more related to the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). From my previous experience, I know broadly two types of citation systems (Vancouver and Harvard). I have tried to correlate what was presented in the course pack with what I know.

However, it would be more helpful if we had some of the common classifications and then narrowed the scope to the purpose of our sessions. Overall, I am happy and feel comfortable with all the approaches.

REFERENCES

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